

Supplementary Table S1: Taxonomic grouping, climate and habitat details for species with collagen (I) sequences present on BLAST/P.

*= α 3 chain labelled as such on BLAST/P. All other samples had α 3 chains labelled as α 1 variants.

¹At least two different sequences are available for this chain of this species.

Species	Common Name	Class	Order	Family	A1	A2	A3	Climate	Optimal Temp.	Habitat
1 <i>Acipenser schrenckii</i>	Amur sturgeon	Actinopterygii	Acipenseriformes	Acipenseridae	Y	Y	N	Temperate	10°C—20°C	Anadromous
2 <i>Anguilla japonica</i>	Japanese eel	Actinopterygii	Anguilliformes	Anguillidae	Y	Y	Y*	Subtropical	4°C—27°C	Catadromous
3 <i>Oryzias latipes</i>	Ricefish species	Actinopterygii	Beloniformes	Adrianichthyidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	18°C—24°C	Freshwater/Brackish
4 <i>Oryzias melastigma</i>	Ricefish species	Actinopterygii	Beloniformes	Adrianichthyidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Freshwater/Brackish
5 <i>Astyanax mexicanus</i>	Mexican tetra	Actinopterygii	Characiformes	Characidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Freshwater
6 <i>Pygocentrus nattereri</i>	Red-bellied pirahna	Actinopterygii	Characiformes	Serrasalminidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	23°C—27°C	Freshwater
7 <i>Clupea harengus</i>	Atlantic herring	Actinopterygii	Clupeiformes	Clupeidae	Y	Y	N	Temperate	1°C—18°C	Marine/Brackish
8 <i>Carassius auratus</i>	Goldfish	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y	Y	Y*	Subtropical	0°C—41°C	Freshwater
9 <i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	Grass carp	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y	Y	N	Subtropical	0°C—35°C	Freshwater
10 <i>Danio rerio</i>	Zebrafish	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y	Y	Y*	Tropical	18°C—24°C	Freshwater
11 <i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	Silver carp	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y	Y	N	Subtropical	6°C—28°C	Freshwater
12 <i>Sinocyclocheilus anshuiensis</i>	Cave fish	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y ¹	Y ¹	Y ¹	Subtropical	Unreported	Freshwater
13 <i>Sinocyclocheilus grahami</i>	Golden line fish	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y ¹	Y ¹	Y	Temperate	Unreported	Freshwater
14 <i>Sinocyclocheilus rhinoceros</i>	[none given]	Actinopterygii	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	Y	Y ¹	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Freshwater
15 <i>Cyprinodon variegatus</i>	Sheepshead minnow	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Cyprinodontidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	-1.9°C—43°C	Brackish
16 <i>Fundulus heteroclitus</i>	Mummichog	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Fundulidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	10°C—24°C	Marine/Brackish
17 <i>Nothobranchius furzeri</i>	Turquoise killifish	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Nothobranchiidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	23°C—30°C	Freshwater
18 <i>Poecilia formosa</i>	Amazon molly	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Poeciliidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Freshwater/Brackish
19 <i>Poecilia latipinna</i>	Sailfin molly	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Poeciliidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	20°C—28°C	Marine/Brackish
20 <i>Poecilia mexicana</i>	Shortfin molly	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Poeciliidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	22°C—28°C	Freshwater/Brackish
21 <i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	Southern platyfish	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Poeciliidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	18°C - 25°C	Freshwater
22 <i>Austrofundulus limnaeus</i>	[none given]	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Rivulidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	22°C—26°C	Freshwater
23 <i>Kryptolebias marmoratus</i>	Mangrove killifish	Actinopterygii	Cyprinodontiformes	Rivulidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	18°C—24°C	Freshwater/Brackish
24 <i>Esox lucius</i>	Northern pike	Actinopterygii	Esociformes	Esocidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	10°C—28°C	Freshwater
25 <i>Gadus morhua</i>	Atlantic cod	Actinopterygii	Gadiformes	Gadidae	Y	Y	Y*	Temperate	0°C—15°C	Marine/Brackish
26 <i>Gasterosteus aculeatus</i>	Three-spined stickleback	Actinopterygii	Gasterosteiformes	Gasterosteidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	4°C—20°C	Anadromous
27 <i>Lepisosteus oculatus</i>	Spotted gar	Actinopterygii	Lepisosteiformes	Lepisosteidae	Y	Y	N	Temperate	12°C—20°C	Freshwater/Brackish
28 <i>Paramormyrops kingsleyae</i>	[none given]	Actinopterygii	Osteoglossiformes	Mormyridae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Freshwater
28 <i>Scleropages formosus</i>	Golden dragon fish	Actinopterygii	Osteoglossiformes	Osteoglossidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	24°C—30°C	Freshwater
30 <i>Seriola dumerili</i>	Greater amberjack	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Carangidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Marine
31 <i>Seriola lalandi dorsalis</i>	Yellowtail amberjack	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Carangidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	18°C—24°C	Marine/Brackish
32 <i>Haplochromis burtoni</i>	[none given]	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Cichlidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	20°C—25°C	Freshwater
33 <i>Haplochromis nyererei</i>	Nyerere's Victoria cichlid	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Cichlidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	22°C—28°C	Freshwater
34 <i>Maylandia zebra</i>	Zebra mbuna	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Cichlidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	22°C—28°C	Freshwater
35 <i>Neolamprologus brichardi</i>	[none given]	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Cichlidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	22°C—25°C	Freshwater
36 <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Nile tilapia	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Cichlidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	14°C—33°C	Freshwater/Brackish
37 <i>Boleophthalmus pectinirostris</i>	Great blue spotted mudskip	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Gobiidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	26°C—30°C	Marine/Brackish
38 <i>Labrus bergylta</i>	Ballan wrasse	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Labridae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	Unreported	Marine
39 <i>Lates calcarifer</i>	Barramundi	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Latidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	15°C—28°C	Catadromous
40 <i>Notothenia coriiceps</i>	Black rockcod	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Nototheniidae	Y	Y	Y	Polar	Unreported	Marine
41 <i>Acanthochromis polyacanthus</i>	Spiny chromis damselfish	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Pomacentridae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Marine
42 <i>Amphiprion ocellaris</i>	Ocellaris clownfish	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Pomacentridae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Marine
43 <i>Stegastes partitus</i>	Bicolour damselfish	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Pomacentridae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Marine
44 <i>Larimichthys crocea</i>	Large yellow croaker	Actinopterygii	Perciformes	Sciaenidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	Unreported	Marine/Brackish
45 <i>Cynoglossus semilaevis</i>	Half-smooth tongue sole	Actinopterygii	Pleuronectiformes	Cynoglossidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Marine/Brackish

46	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	Olive flounder	Actinopterygii	Pleuronectiformes	Paralichthyidae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	Unreported	Marine
47	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	Coho salmon	Actinopterygii	Salmoniformes	Salmonidae	Y	Y ¹	Y ¹	Temperate	0°C—25°C	Anadromous
48	<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>	Rainbow trout	Actinopterygii	Salmoniformes	Salmonidae	Y ¹	Y ¹	Y*	Subtropical	10°C—24°C	Anadromous
49	<i>Oncorhynchus tshawytscha</i>	Chinook salmon	Actinopterygii	Salmoniformes	Salmonidae	Y ¹	Y	Y ¹	Temperate	0°C—25°C	Anadromous
50	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Atlantic salmon	Actinopterygii	Salmoniformes	Salmonidae	Y ¹	Y ¹	Y ¹	Temperate	2°C—9°C	Anadromous
51	<i>Salvelinus alpinus</i>	Arctic char	Actinopterygii	Salmoniformes	Salmonidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	4°C—16°C	Anadromous
52	<i>Ictalurus punctatus</i>	Channel catfish	Actinopterygii	Siluriformes	Ictaluridae	Y	Y	Y	Subtropical	10°C—32°C	Freshwater
53	<i>Monopterus albus</i>	Asian swamp eel	Actinopterygii	Synbranchiformes	Synbranchidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	25°C—28°C	Freshwater/Brackish
54	<i>Hippocampus comes</i>	Tiger tail seahorse	Actinopterygii	Syngnathiformes	Syngnathidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	Unreported	Marine
55	<i>Dichotomyctere nigroviridis</i>	Green spotted puffer	Actinopterygii	Tetraodontiformes	Tetraodontidae	Y	Y	Y	Tropical	24°C—28°C	Freshwater/Brackish
56	<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	Japanese pufferfish	Actinopterygii	Tetraodontiformes	Tetraodontidae	Y	Y	Y	Temperate	Unreported	Marine/Brackish
57	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i>	Small spotted catshark	Chondrichthyes	Carcharhiniformes	Scyliorhinidae	Y	Y	N	Subtropical	Unreported	Marine
58	<i>Callorhynchus milii</i>	Elephant fish	Chondrichthyes	Chimaeriformes	Callorhynchidae	Y	Y	N	Subtropical	10°C—20°C	Marine
59	<i>Rhincodon typus</i>	Whale shark	Chondrichthyes	Orectolobiformes	Rhincodontidae	Y	Y	N	Subtropical	18°C—30°C	Marine
60	<i>Latimeria chalumnae</i>	Coelacanth	Sarcopterygii	Coelacanthiformes	Latimeriidae	Y	Y	N	Temperate (demersal)	13°C—25°C	Marine

Supplementary Table S2: Concatenated and aligned collagen (I) sequences (n=67) for 60 species of fish in this study, including $\alpha 1$, $\alpha 2$ and [where available] $\alpha 3$ chains. X = amino acid unknown; dash (---) = alignment tool.

>Acipenseriformes_Acipenseridae_Acipenser_schrenckii

QMSYGYDEKSGGGMSAPGPMGPMGPRGPPGASNGPQGFPGPHGEPGEPGASGAMGPRGPAGPPGKNGDDGESGKPRPGERGPGSPQGARGFPGTGPLPGIKGHRGFSGLDGAKGDSGP
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KAPDAGPGPMGLMGPRGSPGPPGPAQGFQGHGEPGEPGQTGPVARGPTGPPGKAGDDGNPGRSGKPGDRGTGGAQQARGFPGTGPLPGMKGHRGYTGLDGSKGEVGAAGVKGETGAR
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GESGPNASGPAGPRGPSGERGEVGPAGAPGFAGPPGADGQPGARGERGGPKGDIGPQGPAGSSGPAGPSGPPGPPGPRGDVGPMTGFPGSAGRVGGPGPAGISGPPGPPGNAGKD
GPRGARGDSGPAGRPEQGMVGPSPGMAGEKGPSGESGPPGPPGISGSPGVLGSPGIVLPGSRGDRGLPGGAGGTGESGKIGPAGAQQPRAAGNMGAPGMTGAPGEAGRDGHPGNDGPPGR
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>Anguilliformes_Anguillidae_Anguilla_japonica

QMSHGYDEKSGGGAMPVPGPMGPMGPRGPPGPPGASGPQGFPGPHGEPGEPGASGAMGPRGPAGPPGKNGEDGESGKPRGGERGAPGPPGARGFPGTGPLPGIKGHRGFSGLDGAKGDTGP
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PAGPRGPAGSAGSPGKDGMSGLPGPIGPPGPRGRTGEIGPAGPPGPPGPPGPPGPPGGGDFMGFIAQPAQEKAPDPFR-
HYRQYDGSKGPDPGPGPAGMMGATGPQGPPGAPGPQGFQGHGEPGEPGQSGPVGPRGPPGPPGKSGEDGNNRPGPKPDRGTSQAQARGFPPTPLPGMKGHRGYTGLDGRKGEPPGAG
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>Beloniformes_Adrianichthyidae_Oryzias_latipes

QMSGGYDDKS--

PAMPVPGPMGPMGSRGPPGPPGASGPQGFPGPEGEAGAPGPMGPRGPAGPPGKNGEDGESGKPRAGERGPPGPPQGARGFPPTPLPGIKGHRGFSGLDGAAGDGTGPAGPKGEAGTPGE
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RGPAGPHGPPGKDGRAGAHGTIGAPGARGPPGFSGPAGPAGAPGLPAPPAGGGYDVSGGYDE-YRQMS-FDPSKSSG--
PPVPGPMGMLGPRGPPGPPGASGPQGFNGPPGEPGEPGASGPMGPRGPPGPKNGDDGEPGKPRPGERGSAGPQGARGFPPTPLPGIKGHRGFSGLDGAAGPAGNPGSDGNPGAKGSPGMAGITGAPGMPGMRGPP
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QMSGGYDSKS--

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PGPQGSVAVGPKGNNGEPGAPGHKGEPAKGEPAVGGQGPVPSGEEGKRGARGEPGAPGSPGAGERGGAGARGFPADGAPGPKGAPGERGPAGIAGPKGNTGESGRPGEPGLPGAAGL
TGSPGSPGPDGKTGPAGPPGQDGRPGPPGSAGTRGQPGVMGFPGPKGAAGESGKPGERGAAGVPPGVIAGKDGDLGAPGAPGAPGDRGEQGAAGPPGFQGLPPPPSPGESGKPGEQGIP
GDAGAAGPAGSRGERGFPGERGAQGPAGPSGVRGSPGSDGAKGDAGAPGAPGAQGGPPLQGMMPGERGAAGLPLKGDGRDGGPKIDGAPGKDGIRGLAGPIGAPGPPGASGEKGEVGP
GPAGPTGARGAPGERGEHGPSGAPGAGPPGADGQPGAKGESGDAGAKGDAGPPGPSGVPVAVGAPGSPGAPGATGAKGARGAPGPPGASGFPGAAGRVPVPPGPAGNVGAPGAPGAPGKEGAKGV
RGETGPAGRSGEPPGVPVGPAGEKSGPGDGPAGAAGIPGPQGIAGQRGIVGLPQQRGERGFPGMPGPSGEPGKQGSAGPGERGPPGPMGPPGLSGPPGEAGREGSPGAEGAPGRDGAAGPK
GDRGESGPAGAPGAPGAPGVPVGPAGKSGDRGETGPAGPAGPAGARGPAGPQGPGRGDKGETGEQDRIKGHGRGFSGLQGPVPSGAPGEPGQGPAGSSGPAGPRGPPGSSGAMGKDG
NGLPPIGPPGPRGRTGDIGPAGPPGPPGPPGPPGSSGGFDFGFVAQPQKEKAPDPLRYHYRQYDIGKQPDGPGPMGIMGPRGPQGHNGPPGAQGLQGHGEPGEPGSPGPMGSTGPPGPPG

KTGDDGNPGKAGKSGERGILGPQGARGFPPTPLPGLKGHRYPGIDGRKGEPEGAVGVKGEPPSAGENGSPGQMGSRGLSGERGRIGSAGGAGSRGSDGSTGAAGPAGPMGSGGPPGFPGAPGA
KGEAGPAGSTGPTGPAGPRGEPGSAGAGGPVGGPNPNGLPGAKGEIGLRGVAGVPGFPGPRGNAGLQGAAGPPGPRNGGDPGAGVKGETGARGEPPNAGVPGLAGPSGEEGKRGGPGE
AGNSGAVGRAGQRGVPGPRGLPGGDGRVGGIGLPGARGPSGSAGGKGGPPGDAGRPEPGLPGARGLPGNTGISGSPGKEGPAGAFGLEGRNGPPGPTGPRGQPGAIGFPGPKGPSGLTGKNGDKG
AVGPAGARGAAGADGNPGGQGGVFGATGEKGERGPAGAPGFQGLPGPAGPGEAGKLGDRGMPGDAGVPGPAGVRGERGPPGESGAMGPIGIMGSRGSPHGPDPGGKGEPPGGVGLIGTV
GPAGGAGLPGERGVAGIPGGKGAKEAGARGPDGNVGRDGARGAVGAVGPPGPAGAVGDKGEAGAFGAPGAAGPRGTPGERGEVGPAGPPGFSGPPGADGQAGARGEKGRGPKGEVGGSGA
AGAAGASGPAGPSGPAGPVGPRGSNGSPGATGFPGAAGRVGAPGPPGIAGPVGHPGPPGKEGSRGPRGDAGAIGRPGEQGMGGGSGPAGEKGPSGEIGPPGPPGTSGPSGVIGSRGITGLPGARG
DRGLPGGSGATGEVGRGLGPAGPAGQRGLAGPVGAPGMNGAPGEAGRDGNPGADGAPGRSGSPGYKDRGEPGPTGLPGGAGAPGAHQAGPVGKTGNRGESGPVGPVGMVGPAGQRGAAG
AQGARGEKGVAGDKGDRGMKGMRGHTGLQGLPGPAGAHGEPGLPGITGPSGSRGLPGPSGPPGKSGRDGHSAGIAGPPGVRGPNGHQGPVGGPGLPGAPGLPGAAGGAYEIGGYESDYR-----

Supplementary Table S3: Eight soft fossil calibrations taken from Benton *et al.*, 2015 for the Bayesian clock analysis.

Fossil Calibrations	Hard minimum age (Ma)	Soft maximum age* (Ma)	Mean age (Ma)	Reference
Crown Gnathostomes (root)	420.7	468.4	443.4	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Crown Chondrichthyans	333.6	422.4	375.9	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Crown Osteichthyans	420.7	444.9	432.2	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Crown Neopterygians	250.0	331.1	288.6	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Crown Teleosts	151.2	252.7	199.6	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Crown Clupeocephala	150.9	235.0	191.0	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Oryzias–Gasterosteus	69.7	130.8	98.8	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015
Oryzias–Cichlidae	49.1	130.8	88.0	Benton <i>et al.</i> , 2015

*The soft maximum was included as the 95th percentile of an offset gamma distribution in which the shape parameter=3. Each calibration therefore included a 5% tail which exceeded the age of the soft maximum.

Reference: Benton MJ, Donoghue PC, Asher RJ, Friedman M, Near TJ, Vinther J. Constraints on the timescale of animal evolutionary history. *Palaeontologia Electronica*. 2015;18(1):1D106.

Supplementary Table S4: Collagen (I) sequences organised per tryptic peptide in representative species of mammal, bird, reptile, amphibian, actinopterygian and chondrichthyan. The $\alpha 3$ peptide sequence in *Gadus morhua* is arranged adjacent to $\alpha 1$ for comparative purposes, as the $\alpha 3$ chain is thought to have evolved from the $\alpha 1$ chain. The final column aligns traditional nomenclature with current proposed nomenclature from Brown *et al.* "On the standardization of ZooMS nomenclature." *Journal of Proteomics* 235 (2021): 104041.

Collagen (I) Sequence	Peptide Code	MAMMAL	BIRD	REPTILE	AMPHIBIAN	CHONDRICHTHYAN	ACTINOPTERYGIAN	ACTINOPTERYGIAN	Proposed ZooMS Nomenclature from Brown <i>et al.</i> , 2021*	
		<i>Rattus norvegicus</i> (Brown rat)	<i>Gallus gallus</i> (Chicken)	<i>Chelonia mydas</i> (Green turtle)	<i>Xenopus sp.</i> (Clawed frog)	<i>Scyliorhinus canicula</i> (Catshark)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> (Atlantic cod)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> (Atlantic cod)		
Assumulated Position	Code COL1A1	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 1$)	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 1$)	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 1$)	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 1$)	Code COL1A1	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 1$)	Code COL1A3	Peptide Sequence ($\alpha 3$)	Amino Acid Code
1 – 9	T1	QMSYGYDEK	QMSYGYDEK	QLAYGYDEK	QMSYGYDEK	T1	XXXXXXX	T1	QMSYTDHSK	N/A (N-telopeptide)
10 – 26	T2	SAGVAVPMPGMPGPR	SAGVAVPMPGMPGPR	SVVGLSMPGMPGPR	SAGVSMPPGMPGMPGPR	T2	XXXXXXXXXXGPMGPR	T2	SSGNPSPGMPGMPGMR	1–9
27 – 59	T3	GLPGPPGAPGQGFQGGPGEPEGASGPMGPR	GLPGPPGAPGQGFQGGPGEPEGASGPMGPR	GLPGPPGSPGQGFQGGPGEPEGASGPMGPR	GPPGSPGSPGQGFQGGPGEPEGSSGAMGPR	T3	GSPGAGASXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXGPMGPR	T3	GXPGGPAGPQGFQGGPGEPEGASGPMGSR	10–42
60 – 67	T4	GPPGPPGK	GPAGPPGK	GPAGPPGK	GPAGPPGK	T4	GPAGPPGK	T4	GAGGPPGK	43–50
68 – 76	T5	NGDDGEAGK	NGDDGEAGK	NGDDGEAGK	NGDDGEAGK	T5	NGDDGEAGK	T5	NGDDGEAGK	51–59
77 – 79	T6	PGR	PGR	PGR	PGR	T6	AGR	T6	PGR	60–62
80 – 83	T7	PGR	PGR	PGR	PGR	T7	PGDR	T7	NGER	63–66
84 – 92	T8	GPPGQGAR	GPPGQGAR	GAPGQGAR	GPPGQGAR	T8	GAPGQGAR	T8	GSSGQGAR	67–75
93 – 104	T9	GLPGTAGLPGMK	GLPGTAGLPGMK	GLPGTAGLPGMK	GLPGTAGLPGMK	T9	GLPGTAGLPGMK	T9	GFPGTPLPGIK	76–87
105 – 107	T10	GHR	GHR	GHR	GHR	T10	GHR	T10	GHR	88–90
108 – 116	T11	GFSGLDGAK	GFSGLDGAK	GFSGLDGAK	GFSGLDGAK	T11	GFSGLDGAK	T11	GFSGLDGAK	91–99
117 – 125	T12	GDTGPAGPK	GDTGPAGPK	GDTGPAGPK	GDTGPAGPK	T12	GDSGPAGPK	T12	GDSGPAGPK	100–108
126 – 143	T13	GEPGSPGENGAPQGMGPR	GEPGSPGENGAPQGMGPR	GEPGSPGENGAPQIGPR	GEPGSPGENGAPQVGPGR	T13	GETGSPGENGAPQAMGAR	T13	GEGGASGENGIPGAMGAR	109–126
144 – 149	T14	GLPGER	GLPGER	GLPGER	GLPGER	T14	GVPGER	T14	GLPGER	127–132
150 – 151	T15	GR	GR	GR	GR	T15	GR	T15	GR	133–134
152 – 161	T16	PGPSGAGAR	PGPSGAGAR	PGPSGAGAR	PGPSGAGAR	T16	SGAPGAGAR	T16	PGSAGPSGAR	135–144
162 – 191	T17	GNDGAVGAAGPPGPTGPTGPPGFGAA GAK	GNDGAVGAAGPPGPTGPTGPPGFGAA GAK	GNDGAPGAAGPTGPTGPTGPPGFGAV GAK	GNDGAPGAAGPPGPTGPTGPPGFGV GPK	T17	GNDGAAGGAGAPGVPGAGPPGFGAPGAK	T17	GNDGAAGGAGPPGPTGPTGPPGFGAGAK	145–174
192 – 200	T18	GEAGPQGAR	GETGPQGAR	GETGPQGAR	GDAGPQGAR	T18	GEAGVAGGR	T18	GEGGAQGR	175–183
201 – 209	T19	GSEGPQGR	GSEGPQGR	GSEGPQGR	GSEGPQGR	T19	GSEGPQGR	T19	GSEGPQGR	184–192
210 – 236	T20	GEPGPPGAGAAGPAGNPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAGAAGPAGNPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAGAAGPAGNPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAGAAGPAGNPGADGQPGAK	T20	GEPGAAGPAGTPAGNAGSDGQAGAK	T20	GEPGPPGAGAAGPAGNPGADGQPGAK	193–219
237 – 254	T21	GATGAPGIAGAPGPGAR	GATGAPGIAGAPGPGAR	GATGAPGIAGAPGPGAR	GATGAPGIAGAPGPGAR	T21	GATGAPGMSGAPGPGAR	T21	GSPGAAGSAGAPGFPGR	220–237
255 – 269	T22	GSPGQGPSGAPGPK	GSPGQGPSGAPGPK	GSPGQGPSGAPGPK	GAPGQGPSGAPGPK	T22	GSPGAAGVAVGSPGPK	T22	GPPGQGPSGAPGPK	238–252
270 – 281	T23	GNSGEPGAPGNK	GNSGEPGAPGNK	GNSGEPGAPGNK	GNSGEPGAPGNK	T23	GNTGEGGAPGSK	T23	GNTGEGHAAGAK	253–264
282 – 287	T24	GDTGAK	GDTGAK	GDTGAK	GDTGAK	T24	GETGK	T24	GESGK	265–270
288 – 307	T25	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	T25	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	T25	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	271–290
308 – 308	T26	R	R	R	R	T26	R	T26	R	291
309 – 311	T27	GAR	GAR	GAR	GAR	T27	GAR	T27	GGR	292–294
312 – 326	T28	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	T28	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	T28(1)+(2)	GEPGPAVQGGPPGAGEEGK	295–309
327 – 332	T29	GAPGSR	GAPGSR	GAPGSR	GAPGSR	T29	GAPGSR	T29	GAPGSR	310–315
333 – 344	T30	GFPADGIAGPK	GFPADGIAGPK	GFPADGIAGPK	GFPADGIAGPK	T30	GFPADGIAGPK	T30	GLPGTDGAGGK	316–327
345 – 350	T31	GPAGER	GPAGER	GPAGER	GPAGER	T31	GVPGER	T31	GAPGER	328–333
351 – 359	T32	GSPGAVGPK	GSPGAVGPK	GSPGAVGPK	GSPGAVGPK	T32	GPGPLGK	T32	GSPGAVGPK	334–342
360 – 367	T33	GSPGAGR	GSPGAGR	GSPGAGR	GSPGAGR	T33	GATGEPGR	T33	GSTGESGR	343–350

368	–	377	T34	PGEAGLPGAK	PGEAGLPGAK	PGEPLPGAK	PGEPLPGAK	T34	PGEAGLPGAR			T34	NGEPLSGAK		T34	PGEPLVTGSK		351–360
378	–	391	T35	GLTGSPPSPGPDGK	GLTGSPPSPGPDGK	GLTGSPPSPGPDGK	GLTGSPPSPGPDGK	T35	GLTGSPPSPGADGK			T35	GMTSPSPGPDGK		T35	GVTGSPPSPGPDGK		361–374
392	–	403	T36	TGPPGAGQDGR	TGPPGAGQDGR	TGTPGAGQDGR	TGPAGAGQDGR	T36	PGPAGTQDGR			T36	LGNGAPQDGR		T36	TGSPGAGQDGR		375–386
404	–	413	T37	PGAGPPGAR	PGAGPPGAR	PGAAGPPGAR	PGPPPGGAR	T37	AGPPGSAGPR			T37	PGPPPGVGAR		T37	SGGAGPAGSR		387–396
414	–	425	T38	GQAGVMGFPGPK	GQAGVMGFPGPK	GPAGVMGFPGPK	GQSGVMGFPGPK	T38	GQPGVMGFPGPK			T38	GQPGIMGFPGPK		T38	GQPGVMGFPGTK		397–408
426	–	433	T39	GTAGEPGK	GAAGEPGK	GAAGEPGK	GAAGEPGK	T39	GAAGEPGK			T39	GAAGEGK		T39	GTTGESGK		409–416
434	–	437	T40	AGER	AGER	AGER	AGER	T40	AGER			T40	AGER		T40	AGER		417–420
438	–	451	T41	GVPVPGAVGAPGAK	GAPVPGAVGAAGK	GVPVPGAVGAPGK	GVAGPPVAVGLPGK	T41	GPGVPGAVGPAK			T41	GVMGPNVGTGAPGK		T41	GAAGNTGAVGAPGK		421–434
452	–	470	T42	DGEAGAQGAPGPA GPAGER	DGEAGAQGPPGPTG PAGER	DGEAGAQGPPGAA GPSGER	DGDAGAQGPPGPA GPSGER	T42	DGDVAGPAAGAP AGATGER			T42	DGDVAGPAGSPPA GPSGER		T42	DGDVAGPAGPSPPA GGAGEK		435–453
471	–	496	T43	GEQGPAGSPGFQGL PGAPGPPGEAGK	GEQGPAGAPGFQGL PGAPGPPGEAGK	GEQGPAGSPGFQGL PGAPGAGESGK	GEQGPAGGPFQGL PGPPGAGESGK	T43	GEQGPAGGPFQGL GLPAGSAGPAGESGK			T43	GEQGPAGGPFQGL PGPPGAGESGK		T43	GEGGPPGSPGFQGL PGPPGAGESGK		454–479
497	–	515	T44	PGEQVPGDLGAPG PSGAR	PGEQVPGNAGAP GPAGAR	SEQVQVPGDAGAPG PAGR	PGEQVPGDVGPSG PAGR	T44	PGEQVPGDVGAPG PAGR			T44	PGEQVPGDVGAPG PAGR		T44	PGEQVPGDVGAPG PAGR		480–498
516	–	518	T45	GER	GER	GER	GER	T45	GER			T45	GER		T45	GDR		499–501
519	–	524	T46	GFPGER	GFPGER	GFPGER	GFPGER	T46	GFLGER			T46	GFPGER		T46	GVPGER		502–507
525	–	536	T47	GVQGPAGPAGPR	GVQGPAGPAGPR	GVQGPAGPAGPR	GVQGPAGPAGPR	T47	GAAGITGAPGER			T47	GAPGALGPAGGR		T47	GSNGSPGPTGPR		508–519
537	–	548	T48	GNNGAPGNDGAK	GANGAPGNDGAK	GNGAPGNDGAK	GSNGAPGNDGAK	T48	GGVSGPNDGPK			T48	GGPSAGNDGAK		T48	GAPGSPGNDGAK		520–531
549	–	572	T49	GDTGAPGAPGSOQA PGLQGMPPER	GDAGAPGAPGNEG PPGLEGMPGER	GDAGAPGSPGNQG PPGLEGMPGER	GEAGSAGPAGGQGP PGLQGMPPER	T49	GDAGAPGAPGSSQ GTPGIQGMPPER			T49	GDAGAPGNGGAQ GTPGLQGMPPER		T49	GETGAGGAPGNG GSPGMQGMPPER		532–555
573	–	581	T50	GAAGLPGPK	GAAGLPGAK	GAAGLPGAR	GAGLPGAK	T50	GMSLPGAK			T50	GAAGLPGK		T50	GSSLPGAK		556–564
582	–	584	T51	GDR	GDR	GDR	GDR	T51	GVR			T51	GDR		T51	GER		565–567
585	–	590	T52	GDAGPK	GDGPK	GDGGPK	GDQGVK	T52	GESGPK			T52	GDHGAK		T52	GDGGAK		568–573
591	–	598	T53	GADGSPGK	GADGAPGK	GADGAPGK	GSDGAPGK	T53	GGDGAPGK			T53	GTDGAPGK		T53	GGEGGAGK		574–581
599	–	602	T54	DGVR	DGVR	DGVR	DGVR	T54	DGGR			T54	DGGR		T54	DGGR		582–585
603	–	620	T55	GLTGPVPGPAGAPGDK	GLTGPVPGPAGAPGDK	GLTGPVPGPAGAPGDK	GLTGPVPGPAGAPGDK	T55	GMTGAPVPGHSG APGK			T55	GMTGPVPGHSG APGDK		T55	GMSGAPVPGHSG APGDK		586–603
621	–	635	T56	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR	T56	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR			T56	GEAGPPGAPGPTGAR		T56	GEGGAPGAPGPTGAR		604–618
636	–	641	T57	GAPGDR	GAPGDR	GAPGDR	GAPGER	T57	GAPGER			T57	GAPGER		T57	GSPGER		619–624
642	–	665	T58	GEPGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK	GEPGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK	T58	GESGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK			T58	GESGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK		T58	GESGPPGAPGAPGADGQPGAK		625–648
666	–	674	T59	GEPDGTGAK	GETGDAGAK	GETGDAGAK	GEQGDAGAK	T59	GEVSDSGPK			T59	GEAGDNGAK		T59	GESGAPGK		649–657
675	–	701	T60	GDAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK	GDAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK	GDAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK	GDAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK	T60	GDHPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK			T60	GEAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK		T60	GDAGPPGAPGAPGPIGNVAGAPGPK		658–684
702	–	704	T61	GSR	GAR	GAR	GAR	T61	GAR			T61	GAR		T61	GSR		685–687
705	–	721	T62	GAAGPPGATGFPGA AGR	GSAGPPGATGFPGA AGR	GSAGPPGATGFPGA AGR	GAPGPPGATGFPGA AGR	T62	GAPGPPGATGFPGA AGR			T62	GPAGPPGATGFPGA AGR		T62	GGLGPPGATGFPGA AGR		688–704
722	–	742	T63	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK	T63	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK			T63	VGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK		T63	MGPPGSPGAPGPPGPPGPK		705–725
743	–	746	T64	EGGK	EGGK	EGGK	EGGK	T64	EGAK			T64	EGGK		T64	EGGK		726–729
747	–	749	T65	GPR	GPR	GPR	GPR	T65	GIR			T65	GIR		T65	GGR		730–732
750	–	757	T66	GETGPAGR	GETGPAGR	GETGPAGR	GETGPAGR	T66	GETGSAGR			T66	GETGPAGR		T66	GETGPAGR		733–740
758	–	773	T67	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK	T67	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK			T67	TGELGAPGPPGAPG EK		T67	PGEVPGPAGPPGAPG EK		741–756
774	–	797	T68	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR	T68	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR			T68	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR		T68	GSPGADGAPGAPGPPGQGIAGQR		757–780
798	–	806	T69	GVVGLPGQR	GVVGLPGQR	GVVGLPGQR	GTVGLPGMR	T69	GIVGMSGVR			T69	GIVGMSGVR		T69	XXXXXXXXXX		781–789
807	–	809	T70	GER	GER	GER	GER	T70	GER			T70	GER		T70	XXX		790–792
810	–	823	T71	GFPGLPGSPGEPGK	GFPGLPGSPGEPGK	GFPGLPGSPGEPGK	GFPGLPGSPGEPGK	T71(1)+(2)	GSMGLSGK	TGEPGK		T71	GFPGLPGSPGEPGK		T71	XXXXXXXXXX		793–806
824	–	833	T72	QGPSGASGER	QGPSGASGER	QGPSGSSGER	QGPSGSSGER	T72	AGPVGAPGDR			T72	AGSSGPPGER		T72	QGPSGPPGER		807–816

834	–	853	T73	GPPGPMGPPGLAGP PGEAGR	GPPGPMGPPGLAGP PGEAGR	GPPGPMGPPGLAGP PGEAGR	GPPGPMGPPGLAGP PGEAGR	T73	GPPGPMGPPGLA ASGEVGR		T73	GPPGPMGPPGASG ANGEAGR		817–836
854	–	865	T74	EGSPGAEGSPGR	EGAPGAEGAPGR	EGSPGAEGAPGR	EGAPGAEGAPGR	T74	EGAPGAEGAPGR		T74	EGSTGHDGAPGR		837–848
866	–	872	T75	DGAPGAK	DGAAGPK	DGAAGPK	DGAAGPK	T75	DGAAGPK		T75	DGPAGAK		849–855
873	–	875	T76	GDR	GDR	GDR	GDR	T76	GDR		T76	GDR		856–858
876	–	901	T77	GETGPAGPPGAPGA PGAPGVPVGPAGK	GETGPAGPPGAPGA PGAPGVPVGPAGK	GETGPAGPPGAPGA PGAPGVPVGPAGK	GETGPAGPPGAPGA PGAPGVPVGPAGK	T77	GETGTSIGIPGAPGA PGAPGVPVGPAGK		T77	GESGNAGQPGAPG APGAPGAVGPPSGK		859–884
902	–	905	T78	NGDR	NGDR	NGDR	NGDR	T78	NGDR		T78	NGDR		885–888
906	–	923	T79	GETGPAGPAGPIGP AGAR	GETGPAGPAGPPGP AGAR	GETGPAGPAGPAGP AGPR	GETGPAGPAGPAGV AGAR	T79	GEAGPSGAPGSPG PMGPR		T79	GETGPAGAAAGPAG PSGAR		889–906
924	–	932	T80	GPAGPQGPGR	GPAGPQGPGR	GAAGPQGPGR	GPAGPQGPGR	T80	GPLGAVGPR		T80	GPAGIAGAR		907–915
933	–	935	T81	GDK	GDK	GDK	GDK	T81	GDR		T81	GDK		916–918
936	–	944	T82	GETGEQGDR	GETGEQGDR	GETGEHGDR	GEAGEQGER	T82	GESGEAGLR		T82	GESGEAGER		919–927
945	–	947	T83	GDK	GDK	GDK	GDK	T83	GDK		T83	GDK		928–930
948	–	950	T84	GHR	GHR	GHR	GHR	T84	GHR		T84	GHR		931–933
951	–	980	T85	GFSGLQGGPPGSPG GEQGGPSGASGAPG PR	GFSGLQGGPPGPA PGEQGGPSGASGAPG PR	GFSGLQGGPPGPGS PGEQGGPSGASGAPG PR	GFSGLQGGPPGPGS SGEQGGPSGASGAPG PR	T85	GFTGMQGLPGPTG PPGEQGGPAGSSGA SGPR		T85	GLNGMQGMPPGPS GSSGDQGPAGSAG PAGPR		934–963
981	–	991	T86	GPPGSAGSPGK	GPPGSAGAAGK	GPPGSAGSPGK	GPPGSAGNPGK	T86	GPPGSAGSPGK		T86	GPPGSAGSPGK		964–974
992	–	1007	T87	DGLNGLPGIPGPPG R	DGLNGLPGIPGPPG R	DGLNGLPGIPGPPG R	DGLNGLPGIPGPPG R	T87	DGASGLPGIPGPPG PR		T87	DGMNGLPGIPGPP GPR		975–990
1008	–	1009	T88	GR	GR	GR	GR	T88	GR		T88	GR		991–992
1010	–	1047	T89	TGDSGAPGPPGPPG PPGPPGPPSSGDFDLS FLPQQPQEK	TGEVGPVPPGPPG PPGPPGPPSSGDFDLS FLPQQPQEK	TGDVGPAGPPGPPG PPGPPGPPSSGDFDLS FLPQQPQEK	TGDVGPAGPPGPPG PPGPPGPPSSGDFDLS FLPQQPQEK	T89	NGDMGPAGPPGA PGVPPGPPSSGDFDLS FDMGFXXXXXXXXXX		T89	SGEMGPAGPPGPPG GPPGPPGAPGGGF DMGFISQPQEK		993–1015
			Code COL1A2	Peptide Sequence (α2)	Peptide Sequence (α2)	Peptide Sequence (α2)	Peptide Sequence (α2)	Code COL1A2	Peptide Sequence (α2)		Code COL1A2	Peptide Sequence (α2)		Amino Acid Code
1	–	5	T1	QYSDK	QYDPSK	XXXXXX	QYDPSK	T1	XXXXXX		T1	QYDHNK		N/A (N-telopeptide)
6	–	20	T2	GVSAGPGMGLMG PR	AADFGPGMGLMG PR	XXXXGQGMGIMG PR	SGGEGPGAGLMGP R	T2	XXXXXXXXXXXXXX		T2	GADTGPMPGM MGMK		1–9
21	–	53	T3	GPPGAVGAPGQGF QGPAGEGEPGQGTG PAGSR	GPPGASGPPGPPGF QGVGEPGEPGQGTG PQGPGR	GAPGTSGPPGAQGF QGPAGEGEPGQGTG PVGAR	GPPGPPGSPGAQGF QGHAGEGEPGQGP GPLGSTGSPGPPGK	T3	XXXXXXXXXGSQG HTGHAGEGEPGQ TGPVGSR		T3	GPPGPPGPPGSPGQ HTGHAGEGEPGQ TGPVGSR		10–42
54	–	61	T4	GPAGPPGK	GPPGPPGK	GPAGPPGK	(AS ABOVE)	T4	GPPGPPGK		T4	GPPGPPGK		43–50
62	–	70	T5	AGEDGHPGK	AGEDGHPGK	SGEDGHPGK	PGEDGHSK	T5	GGDDGNNGR		T5	GGDDGNNGR		51–59
71	–	73	T6	PGR	PGR	PGR	SGR	T6	PGK		T6	PGK		60–62
74	–	77	T7	PGER	PGER	SGER	PGER	T7	PGDR		T7	PGDR		63–66
78	–	86	T8	GVVGPQGAR	GVVGPQGAR	GVPGTQGAR	GTVGSQGAR	T8	GTAGPQGAR		T8	GTAGPQGAR		67–75
87	–	98	T9	GFPPTPLPGFK	GFPPTPLPGFK	GFPPTPLPGFK	GFPPTPLPGFK	T9	GFPPTPLPGMK		T9	GFPPTPLPGMK		76–87
99	–	101	T10	GIR	GIR	GIR	GIR	T10	GHR		T10	GHR		88–90
102	–	110	T11	GHNGLDGLK	GHNGLDGLK	GHNGLDGLK	GHNGLDGLK	T11	XXXXXXXXXX		T11	GYTGIDGRK		91–99
111	–	119	T12	GQPGAQGVK	GQPGTPGK	GQAGAPGK	GGGAVGK	T12	XXXXXXXXXX		T12	GESGASGK		100–108
120	–	137	T13	GEPGAPGENTPGQ AGAR	GEPGAPGENTPGQ PGAR	GEPGAPGENTPGQ AGAR	GETGANGENSGPQ SGAR	T13	GESGAGSSGSPG MAGAR		T13	GESGAGSSGSPG MAGAR		109–126
138	–	143	T14	GLPGER	GLPGER	GLPGER	GLPGER	T14	GTIGER		T14	GTIGER		127–132
144	–	145	T15	GR	GR	GR	GR	T15	GR		T15	GR		133–134
146	–	155	T16	VGAPGAGAR	IGAPGAGAR	VGSPGVPGR	GGPPGAGSR	T16	AGPAGAGAR		T16	AGPAGAGAR		135–144
156	–	185	T17	GSDGVPVGPAGP IGSAGPPGFPAGP K	GSDGSAGTGPAGPI GAAAGPPGFPAGPA K	GSDGSAGTGPAGPI GAAAGPPGFPAGPA K	GSDGSAGTGPAGPI GSAGPPGFPAGPA K	T17	GADGNVPAGPA GPLSSGAPGFPGS PGPK		T17	GADGNVPAGPA GPLSSGAPGFPGS PGPK		145–174
186	–	203	T18	GELGVPVNGPAGP AGPR	GEIGPAGVNGTGP AGPR	GDIGAAGAVGSPG AGPR	GEIGSAGTGSAGAA GPR	T18	GEVGPAGSSGSPG PQGSR		T18	GEVGPAGSSGSPG PQGSR		175–192

204	--	230	T19	GEAGLPLGSGPVGPP GNPGANGLTGAK	GEIGLPGSSGVPVPP GNPGANGLPGAK	GEPGLPGASGVVPP AGNPGANGIAGAK	GEPGPPGALGVVPP AGNPGANGVNGAK	T19	GEAGTNGAGGPV GPPGNPGNNGLN GAK			T19	GEAGTNGAGGPV GPPGNPGNNGLN GAK			193-219
231	--	248	T20	GATGLPVAGAPGL PGPR	GAAGLPVAGAPGL PGPR	GAAGLPVAGAPGL PGPR	GAAGLPVAGAPGL PGPR	T20	GASGAAGVSGAPG FLGAR			T20	GASGAAGVSGAPG FLGAR			220-237
249	--	263	T21	GIPGPVGAAGATGP R	GIPGPPGAPGSGAR	GIPGPAGPAGTAGA R	GIPGPPGSPGAPGAR	T21	GPGPQQGQGA GAR			T21	GPGPQQGQGA GAR			238-252
264	--	275	T22	GLVGEPPAGSK	GLVGEPPAGAK	GLAGEPPAGSK	GLSGDPGVAGGK	T22	GLSGDPGTSGVK			T22	GLSGDPGTSGVK			253-264
276	--	281	T23	GETGNK	GESGNK	GESGNK	GDTGAK	T23	GDSGPK			T23	GDSGPK			265-270
282	--	301	T24	GEPGSAGAQQPPGP SGEEGK	GEPGAAGPPPPGP SGEEGK	GEPGAAGSPGAPG NGEEGK	GEPGSAGPSGAPG SGEEGR	T24	GEPGHHGPQGAP GPNGEEGK			T24	GEPGHHGPQGAP GPNGEEGK			271-290
302	--	302	T25	R	R	R	R	T25	R			T25	R			291
303	--	320	T26	GSPGEPGSAGPAGP PGLR	GSNGEPGSAGPPG PGLR	GSTGEAGTGPPGS AGLR	GPNGEAGSSGAPGN AGLR	T26(1)+(2)	GPSGEAGASGAPG AGIR	GAR		T26(1)+(2)	GPSGEAGASGAPG PR	GAR		292-309
321	--	326	T27	GSPGSR	GEPGSR	GVPGSR	GVPGTR	T27	GAGGSR			T27	GAGGSR			310-315
327	--	334	T28	GLPGADGR	GLPGADGR	GLPGEGR	GLPDPGR	T28	GIPGSEGR			T28	GIPGSEGR			316-323
335	--	344	T29	AGVMGPPGNR	AGVMGPAGNR	AGSMGLAGSR	AGGMGAPGSR	T29	SGPIMPGAR			T29	SGPIMPGAR			324-333
345	--	353	T30	GSTGPAGVR	GASGPVGA	GSPGPAGAR	GASGPAGAR	T30	GATGAGGAR			T30	GATGAGGAR			334-342
354	--	361	T31	GPNGDAGR	GPNGDAGR	GPGGDSGR	GPNGDAGR	T31	GAPGDAGR			T31	GAPGDAGR			343-350
362	--	371	T32	PGEPGLMGPR	PGEPGLMGPR	PGEPGLGPR	PGEPGLGAR	T32	AGETGLTGAR			T32	AGETGLTGAR			351-360
372	--	385	T33	GLPGSPGNVGPAGK	GLPGQPGSPGPAK	GLPGQPGNPGPAK	XXXXXXXXXXXXX	T33	GLPGSPGSSGPPGK			T33	GLPGSPGSSGPPGK			361-374
386	--	397	T34	EGPVGLPGIDGR	EGPVGFPGADGR	EGPVGFPGADGR	XXXXXXXXXXGR	T34	EGASGPAGQDGR			T34	EGASGPAGQDGR			375-386
398	--	407	T35	PGPIGPAGPR	VGPIGPAGNR	VGPIGPAGPR	SGPAGASGR	T35	TGPPGPTGPR			T35	TGPPGPTGPR			387-396
408	--	419	T36	GEAGNIGFPGPK	GEPGNIGFPGPK	GEPGNIGFPGPK	GEPGSIGFPGPK	T36	GQPGVMGFPGPK			T36	GQPGSIGFLGPK			397-408
420	--	427	T37	GPSSGDPGK	GPTGEPGK	GPNGEPGK	GPAGEPGK	T37	GSSGAPGK			T37	GPSGEAGK			409-416
428	--	431	T38	PGEK	PGEK	PGDK	NGDK	T38	PGER			T38	PGDK			417-420
432	--	440	T39	GHPPLAGAR	GNVLAGPR	GNVVGASR	GSQGPSGR	T39	GGSGAAGR			T39	GPAGASGLR			421-429
441	--	464	T40	GAPGPDGNNGAQG PPGVTGNQGA	GAPGPEGNNGAQG PPGVTGNQGA	GAPGPDGNNGVQG PPGVTGNQGA	GAPGPDGNNGAQG PPGLAGNTGDK	T40(1)+(2)	GAFGK	DGEVGAQGP PGVAGPMG AR		T40	GAPGPEGNNGAA GALGPVGGAGEK			430-453
465	--	490	T41	GEQGAPGPPGFQGL PGPSGAGEAGK	GETGPAGPPGFQGL PGPSGAGEAGK	GEQQGAPGPPGFQGL PGPSGAGEAGK	GEQGPAGPFGQGL PGPGAAAGELGK	T41	GEAGPSGGSGFQG SPGLGAVGEPGK			T41	GEQGPAGPFGQ GLPGTAGPAGEAG K			454-479
491	--	494	T42	PGER	PGER	PGDR	HGER	T42	SGNQVVR			T42	HGDR			480-483
495	--	509	T43	GLHGEFGLPGPAGPR	GLHGEFVPGPAGP R	GIPGEFGLPGPAGPR	GAPGDFGPAGPAGP R	T43	GDNGSPGVAGTK			T43	GVPGDQGLAGPA GIK			484-498
510	--	512	T44	GER	GER	GER	GER	T44	GER			T44	GER			499-501
513	--	530	T45	GPPGESGAAGSPGPI GSR	GLPGESGAVGAPGI GSR	GAPGESGAVGPGVS MGSR	GAPGESGAAGPLGA LGPR	T45(1)+(2) (3)	GPPGER	GGK	GPQGLTGR	T45	GTPGVAGTSGPQG SIGAR			502-519
531	--	542	T46	GPSGAPGPDGNK	GPSGPPGPDGNK	GPTGPPGSDGNK	GPTGAPGSDGAK	T46	GASGPPGSDGK			T46	GPAGLPGTDGK			520-531
543	--	566	T47	GEAGAVGAPGSAGA SGPGLPGER	GEPGNVGPAGAPG AGPGGIPGER	GEPGNVGPAGGPP AGPGGIPGER	GEPGAAGLNGALGP SGPGGIPGER	T47	GEIGLVLVGHPG AHGAQGMPPGER			T47	GEPGSVGAAGNAG HQSGGMPGER			532-555
567	--	575	T48	GAAGIPGK	GVAGVPK	GIAGVPK	GAAGVPK	T48	GAAGSIGIK			T48	GGAGTPGK			556-564
576	--	578	T49	GEK	GEK	GEK	GEK	T49	GEK			T49	GEK			565-567
579	--	584	T50	GETGLR	GAPGLR	GLPGLR	GDAGHSGEYGNPR	T50/51/52	GDSGPAGPQGSAG MDGPR			T50	GEGGHR			568-573
585	--	592	T51	GEIGNPGR	GDTGATGR	GEAGATGR	(AS ABOVE)	-	(AS ABOVE)			T51	GPDGNVGR			574-581
593	--	596	T52	DGAR	DGAR	DGSR	DGAR	-	(AS ABOVE)			T52	DGSR			582-585
597	--	614	T53	GAPGAIAGPPAGA SGDR	GLPGAIGAPGAGG AGDR	GIPGAVGSPGAGG PGDR	GPAGASGAPGAGA AGDR	T53	GIPGPVAGPAGPSG PSGDR			T53	GAPGPGPPGPN GANGDK			586-603
615	--	629	T54	GEAGAAGSPGAPG R	GEGGPAGPAGPAGA R	GEAGPAGSAGPAGP R	GESGPAGPSGLAP R	T54	GESGAGHSGSAG PR			T54	GESGSGPSGSPGV R			604-618
630	--	635	T55	GSPGER	GIPGER	GAPGER	GAPGER	T55	GSPGER			T55	GPSGER			619-624

636	-	659	T56	GEVGPAGNPFAGP AGSAGQPGAK	GEPGPVGSFAGP PGAAGQPGAK	GESGPAGNPFAGP PGAAGQTGAK	GEAGPAGSTGFAGP PGAAGHTGVK	T56(1)+(2)	GEAGR	IGPPGFAGPP GADGHSKAK		
660	-	662	T57	GEK	GER	GER	GER	T57	GEK			
663	-	665	T58	GTK	GPK	GQK	GPK	T58/Q9	GVPGGK			
666	-	668	T59	GPK	GPK	GPK	GPK	-	(AS ABOVE)			
669	-	698	T60	GENGIVGPTGPVGA AGPSGPNPAGPAG SR	GETGPTGAIGPIGAS GPPPGVGAAGPAGP R	GEVGLGAIGPAGSS GPAGPIGAAGPAGG R	GESGSPGALGAVGS HGPAGPNPAGTGTG PR	T60/61	GEVGSAGAVGQP GLAGAAGPAGVPG LQGPVSLGQQTG MTGFSGPAGR			
699	-	715	T61	GDDGPPGMTGFPG AAGR	GDAGPPGMTGFPG AAGR	GDAGPSGATGFPGA AGR	GDDGAPGANGFP PAGR	-	(AS ABOVE)			
716	-	736	T62	TGPPGSGITGPPGP PGAAGK	VGPPGAGITGPPGP PGPAGK	TGPPGAGITGPPGP PQSGK	TGAPGAGIVGSPG ATGHPGK	T62/63/64	AGTPGAGATGPQ GPPGPTGNPQPQ PR			
737	-	740	T63	EGIR	DGPR	DGPR	DGPR	-	(AS ABOVE)			
741	-	743	T64	GPR	GPR	GPR	GPR	-	(AS ABOVE)			
744	-	751	T65	GDOQPVGR	GDVGPVGR	GDTGPVGR	GDSGPVGR	T65/66	GDTGPQGR	SGSGGSLGA NGVPGDR		
752	-	767	T66	TGEIGASGPPGFAGE K	TGEQGIAGPPGFAGE K	PGEQIVGPPGFAGE K	PGEQIGGPPQGLIGE K	-	(AS ABOVE)			
768	-	800	T67	GPSGEPGTTGPPGT AGPQGLLAPGILGL PGSR	GPSGEAGAAGPPGT PGPQILGAPGILGL PGSR	GPSGEPGAGPPGT SGPQILGAPGILGL PGSR	GSSGESGAPPPGA SGPSGVLGALGISGL PGAR	T67	GPAGETGSPGPPG GPGPQGLGASAGV HGLPGSR			
801	-	803	T68	GER	GER	GER	GER	T68/69	GDSGLPVSGPHG LPGDTPGSGASGLR			
804	-	827	T69	GQPGIAGALGEPGPL GIAGPPGAR	GLPGIAGALGEPGPL GVSGPPGAR	GLPGISGTTGEPGPA GISGPPGAR	GTPGGPGANGESGP AGPAGSAGSR	-	(AS ABOVE)			
828	-	847	T70	GPPGAVGSPGVNGA PGEAGR	GPSGVPVSPGVNGA PGEAGR	GPSGSPGAPLNGP PGEAGR	GPSGVPVSPGLTGV HGEAGR	T70	GSAGAVGAPAGLTG QNGESGR			
848	-	859	T71	DGNPNSDGPGR	DGNPNSDGPGR	DGNPNSDGPGR	DGNPNSDGPGR	T71/72	DGNPGR	DGPPGPGGQ SGVK		
860	-	866	T72	DGQPGHK	DGAPGFK	DGAPGFK	DGLPGVK	-	(AS ABOVE)			
867	-	869	T73	GER	GER	GER	GER	T73	GER			
870	-	895	T74	GYPGNIGTGAAGA PGPHGVSVPAGK	GAPGNPSPGALGA PGPHGQVGPAGK	GYPGNLAGAAG APGPHGAVGSPGK	GYPGGTGPAGSLGA VGAPGAVGSPGK	T74	GDAGRVSAGALG QPGAHGHVGPAG K			
896	-	899	T75	HGNR	PGNR	PGNR	SGNR	T75	AGNR			
900	-	917	T76	GEVGPAGSVGPVGA VGPR	GDVGPVGPVGPAGA FGPR	GEVGPVGTGSI GAR	RGEVGPVGHAGAVG PAGPR	T76	GEVGPVGTGSI QMGPR			
918	-	926	T77	GPSGQGIR	GLAGPQGPR	GLGGPQGPR	GPSGQGTR	T77	GLAGPQGPR			
927	-	929	T78	GDK	GEK	GEK	GDK	T78	GDK			
930	-	935	T79	GEPGDK	GEVGPDK	GEVGPDK	GEAGER	T79	GETGFAGVR			
936	-	938	T80	GAR	GHR	GPR	GAR	T80	GLK			
939	-	944	T81	GLPGLK	GLPGLK	GMPGFK	GLDGR K	T81	GLR			
945	-	974	T82	GHNGLQGLPGLAGL HGDDGAPGPVGA GPR	GHNGLQGLPGLAGQ HGDDGPPGNNGPA GPR	GHNGLQGLPGLAGH HGDDGAPGSTGPA GPR	GHNGLQGLPGLAGS PGETGAGSNGPSG GPR	T82	GPGGLQGLPVG ISGETGSHGSPG GPR			
975	-	985	T83	GPAGSPGPIGK	GPPGSPGPIGK	GPAGSPGPIGK	GPAGSPGPIGK	T83	GPPGSPGPIGK			
986	-	988	T84	DGR	DGR	DGR	EGR	T84/85	DGGSGHPGSI GHR			
989	-	1001	T85	SGHGPVGPAGVR	NGLPPIGPAGVR	NGLPPIGPAGVR	SGHNGPIGPVGLR	-	(AS ABOVE)			
1002	-	1039	T86	GSQSGQSPGPPGP PGPPGPPVSGGGY DFGFEFGFYR	GSHGSGQSPGPPGP PGPPGPPVSGGGY EVGFDAYYR	GSQSGQSPGPPGP PGPPGPPVSGGGY EIGYDAYYR	GPAGHQGAPPPGP PPGLPAGASGGG YDGGFGGEFFR	T86(1)+(2) +(3)	GR	PGEHGMG PPGSPGAG LPGMAGVPY EVSYDR	EYR	

T56	GEVGPAGSAGFAG PPGADGSPSVR	
T57	GER	
T58/59	GPAGGK	
-	(AS ABOVE)	
T60	GDLGPAGPAGPAG QSGPSGASGPAGP PGGR	
T61	GDNGPSLGTGFPG VGGR	
T62	VGAAGPSGIVGPP GSSGAAGK	
T63	DGPR	
T64	GLR	
T65/66	GDSGAPPPGEGQ MLGPAGLAGDK	
-	(AS ABOVE)	
T67	GPSGSDSPAGAPG TSGPSQGLGGQY VGLPGPR	
T68	GDR	
T69(1)+(2)	XXXGVPGGAGESG R	VGPTGSAG PR
T70	GPSGNIMPGMT GPQGEAGR	
T71	EGNTGNDGPPGR	
T72	PGIAGIK	
T73	GDR	
T74	GEPGNSGPMGMA GAPGSPGQTGA GR	
T75	GGNR	
T76	GESGPGPTGSPG MAGAR	
T77	GAAGPAGPR	
T78	GEK	
T79	GVGGEK	
T80	GER	
T81(1)+(2)	GDK	GLR
T82	GHNGLQGLPGLAG QSGSDSAGPAG PSGPR	
T83	GPAGHPGPPGK	
T84	DGR	
T85	SGSHGTIGAPGAR	
T86	GPPGYLGPAGP SPGLPAGPAGD GYDVSAGGYEYR	

625-648
649-651
652-657
658-687
688-704
705-725
726-729
730-732
733-756
757-789
790-792
793-816
817-836
837-848
849-855
856-858
859-884
885-888
889-906
907-915
916-918
919-924
925-927
928-933
934-963
964-974
975-977
978-990
991-1014

Supplementary Table S5: BLASTP accession codes for each collagen (I) α -chain isoform for the tetraploidy species in this study. Sequences are arbitrarily labelled 'A' and 'B'. Where only one code is listed for a particular α -chain, there is only one isoform present on BLASTP at time of publishing.

Species	Isoform	Accession Code (BLASTP)		
		α 1	α 2	α 3
<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	A	XP_020348842.1	XP_020360620.1	XP_020316038.1
	B		XP_020355638.1	XP_020327438.1
<i>O. mykiss</i>	A	XP_021413219.1	NP_001117679.1	NP_001117678.1
	B	NP_001117649.1	XP_021428324.1	
<i>O. tshawytscha</i>	A	XP_024245808.1	XP_024296660.1	XP_024243872.1
	B	XP_024288724.1		XP_024290020.1
<i>Salmo salar</i>	A	XP_014059932.1	XP_014033985.1	XP_014065361.1
	B	XP_014048044.1	XP_013998297.1	XP_014035319.1
<i>Sinocyclocheilus anshuiensis</i>	A	XP_016307878.1	XP_016317714.1	XP_016348621.1
	B	XP_016314956.1	XP_016314980.1	XP_016343587.1
<i>Sinocyclocheilus grahami</i>	A	XP_016127375.1	XP_016138752.1	XP_016113605.1
	B	XP_016124437.1	XP_016136266.1	
<i>Sinocyclocheilus rhinoceros</i>	A	XP_016408602.1	XP_016385859.1	XP_016368866.1
	B		XP_016398335.1	

Supplementary Table S6: A selection of collagen (I) peptide sequences from *Salmo salar* (Atlantic salmon), showing sequence variations between the two different isoforms of $\alpha 1$ (A1), $\alpha 2$ (A2) and $\alpha 3$ (A3) chains, both variations of which can be visualised in the peptide mass fingerprint for this species (Supplementary Figure S1).

Peptide Code (COL1)	Sequence for Isoform 1	m/z for Isoform 1	Sequence for Isoform 2	m/z for Isoform 2	Amino Acid Substitution(s)	Inset in Figure
A3T47	GGIGSVGPSGPR	1040	GGLGSAGPTGPR	1026	I-L, V-A, S-T	A(1)
A3T15/16	GRPGPAGPSGGR	1081	GRPGPAGSSGAR	1085	P-S, G-A	A(2)
A3T36	VGPAGITGNDGR	1114	VGPAGVTGNDGR	1100	I-V	B
A3T56	GEGGLGGPPGPAGGR	1251	GEGGLGGPPGPTGGR	1281	A-T	C
A2T26 (1)	GSTGEVGATGPAGLR	1329	GSTGEAGATGPAGLR	1301	V-A	D
A3T21	GATGAVGISGAPGFPGSR	1590	GSTGAAGISGAPGFPGTR	1592	A-S, V-A, S-T	E
A1T73	GPPGPMGPPGLAGAPGESGR	1774	GPPGPMGPPGLAGAPGEPGR	1784	S-P	F
A2T56	GEGGPAGPPGFAGPPGSDGQPGPR	2131/47	GEGGPAGPPGFAGPPGSDGQSGPR	2121/37	P-S	G
A1T85	GFTGMQGPSGPAGPSGESGPAGASGPAGPR	2612	GFTGMQGPPGPSGQSGESGPAGASGPAGPR	2685	S-P, A-S, P-Q	H
A3T17/18	GNDGNSGPAGSPGPTGPSGSPGFPGGAGAKGETG TGPQGGR	3412	GNDGNSGPAGSNGPTGPSGAPGFPGGAGAKGETG PQGGR	3399	P-N, S-A	I